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НАГЛАСИ СПРЯМО ИМИГРАНТИТЕ СРЕД БЪЛГАРИТЕ В РЕПРОДУКТИВНА ВЪЗРАСТ: РЕЗУЛТАТИ ОТ НАЦИОНАЛНО АНКЕТНО ПРОУЧВАНЕ

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Резюме: Статията представя резултати от национално представително социологическо проучване на лицата във фертилна възраст в Р България. Фокусът е върху различни аспекти на нагласите на българското общество спрямо имигрантите. Разглежда се и нагласите за включващото обучение на деца на имигранти. Анализът и интерпретацията на резултатите включват важни в интеграционен план характеристики на населението в репродуктивна възраст като пола, възрастта, образованието, семейни характеристики, местоживеенето, работата и доходите. Резултатите показват, че мнозинството хора в българското общество имат по-скоро позитивни нагласи по отношение на имигрантите и включващото образование на децата им, но сред населението се открояват и отделни групи, сред които доминират негативните нагласи.

Ключови думи: имигранти; социални нагласи; включване на имигрантите в образованието.

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ATTITUDES TOWARDS IMMIGRANTS AMONG THE BULGARIANS OF REPRODUCTIVE AGE: NATIONAL SURVEY RESULTS

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Abstract: *The article discusses results from a national representative sociological survey of persons of reproductive age in the Republic of Bulgaria. The focus is on various aspects of the attitudes of Bulgaria's public towards immigrants. The attitudes towards inclusive education for the children of immigrants are also discussed. The analysis and interpretation of the results include important, in terms of inclusion, characteristics of reproductive age persons such as sex, age, education, family characteristics, place of residence, work and income. The results show that Bulgaria's society still is dominated by positive attitudes towards immigrants and the immigrant inclusive education, but among some social groups prevail the negative attitudes.*

Keywords: immigrants; social attitudes; inclusive education of immigrants.

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Introduction

This analysis is part of studies conducted under the project “Measures to overcome the demographic crisis in the Republic of Bulgaria”, funded by the Council of Ministers of the Republic of Bulgaria. Its main objective is to research and present the attitude of the Bulgarians of reproductive age towards one of the most vulnerable groups in Bulgarian society – immigrants. It is aimed at making the research as useful and practical as possible for all stakeholders who make and/or implement policies concerning immigrants in the country.

From a policymaking perspective, it is relevant to note that public opinion and people’s attitudes represent a specific aspect of the political context. In recent years, it is widely noticed that public opinion has often overridden the arguments of experts, including factual evidence, in policy decision-making.¹ This presupposes in itself the practical usefulness of the ongoing analysis.

The attitudes and distances of a majority towards a minority may be a consequence of personal experience. But in the case of Bulgaria, it is much more likely that they are constructed on the basis of stereotyped opinions built in the family and schools, during the process of socialisation and/or through the media and social networks (Tomova, 2009). Although these are hard challenges, the attitudes, prejudices, stereotypes and distances are possible to change. An aim of this analysis is to help find solutions in this regard.

Methodological notes

The results on the distances and attitudes of Bulgarian public aged 18-55 towards immigrants in the analysis below are based on data from the survey “Attitudes towards fertility, family policies and vulnerable communities”. The survey is nationally representative of persons of reproductive age, sampling 1506 adult respondents.

A standardized face-to-face questionnaire was used to survey the opinions on various items among specific groups of Bulgaria’s population: men of reproductive age 18-55 and women of reproductive age 18-50. These age groups partially overlap with that of Bulgaria’s 2018 working-age population (15-64), which provides reason to carefully (and when appropriate) attribute some of the conclusions to it as well.

Pensioners and pre-retirees were completely excluded from the survey, with the exception of a few persons who, given their specific status (military and Ministry of the Interior personnel), fall into the categories in question. In general, these respondents do not affect the results, but it should be borne in mind that the exclusion of persons aged over 55 does not allow conclusions to be drawn for the macro society as a whole. The relative share of persons excluded from the survey is actually about

¹ A textbook example is Bulgaria’s failed attempt to adopt The Council of Europe Convention on preventing and combating violence against women and domestic violence (Istanbul Convention).

one third of Bulgaria's population according to Eurostat data for 2018 (the year in which MarketLinks conducted the fieldwork). It is important to note that those aged 55 and over are among those citizens who are most active in exercising their right to vote, and their opinions weigh not only on issues that directly affect them. These circumstances, linked to the available data, cannot be overcome. Nevertheless, the usefulness of the results is considerable. They relate to a population of at least 3 million people and represent the key age groups for the demographic and economic development of the country.

Representativeness of the results and a relatively small stochastic error is achieved via multi-stage cluster random sampling stratified by NUTS 2 regions, districts and settlement type - capital city, large city, medium town and small settlement. The fieldwork was conducted between 26/02/2018 and 30/03/2018 (Market Links, Methodology Report).

Immigrants in Bulgaria: some context

The Eurostat/NSI statistical definition of an immigrant is useful as a starting point: a person who settles to live on the territory of the Republic of Bulgaria for a period of at least 12 months and previously lived permanently in another country. This definition in itself is not widely known among common people on the subject of migration. This is fully true for the vast majority (perhaps all) of the respondents whose attitudes are discussed below. It is therefore necessary to present the specifics that reveal certain public perceptions of 'immigrants', thereby providing a parallel perspective for sociological interpretation of the survey results.

At the time of the interviews, the respondents whose answers are discussed in the analysis had no clear criteria or definition as to exactly which individuals from the entire diversity of immigrant flows were referred to in the question. They have intuitively oriented themselves about which "immigrants" their answers are valid for, without explicitly specifying whether they are referring to immigrants from Germany, Russia, China, Moldova, Afghanistan, Iraq, etc. or refugees from Syria, Sudan, Somalia, and so on. However, by their answers, one can assume (see Fig. 1) that very often they did so mostly on the basis of information from journalists, politicians and commentators who, as of 2018, were "working" on the topic of "immigrants as a threat" to the Bulgarian nation in most media (including even some sports platforms).

The following lines are based on an analytical reading of more than two hundred pieces of news and commentary articles in Bulgarian-language leading media in the period 2014-2019, which are freely available on electronic platforms and in print media, including through social networks on the Internet. The aim of this review is to summarise the information about immigrants most commonly available to the general public.

Particularly noteworthy is the group of those immigrants who are represented as a threat to various spheres of life in the country. This is most likely the group that respondents visibly refer to when answering the key survey question for this analysis, i.e. whether they approve of their children or grandchildren studying in a class where

children of immigrants also study. This is also the group that the media cover in the vast majority of cases when immigration is stigmatised (including forced migration, i.e. refugees).

It is very likely that prejudiced negative stereotyping of any social group, including immigrants, will lead to rejection, negative attitudes, discrimination and distancing. Any non-individual grounds for unhuman treatment such as the country of origin, religion, skin colour, etc. are unacceptable from a humanist perspective. For full and better understanding of the results however, one should keep in mind the existence of let's name it "a double standard" towards immigrants in today's Bulgarian society – immigrants to whom the principles of humanism are almost unconditionally applied and other immigrants to whom the public demands are very high and whose stereotyped image is characterized by negative features such as fear, presumed non-acceptance and frequently even hatred.

The majority of the media (including those that some public commentators refer to as liberal) and a significant number of conservative-minded politicians are at the heart of creating and spreading the image of immigrants as a threat. Politicians, journalists and political commentators problematise immigrants through the following thematic strands:

- particular aspects of national security - illegal border crossings, countries of origin of refugees/immigrants where extreme conservative and/or fundamentalist political regimes are in power, often linked to terrorist activities and organisations;
- the possible impact of immigrants/refugees on the country's social assistance/protection and health care systems - the amounts paid out as benefits to families staying in temporary detention centres, the health costs associated with them and so on;
- the potential/capacity of immigrants to participate in the economy and the labour market – how fit they are to do quality work, communicating messages to the Roma minority that the immigrant "aliens" are competitors who will take away their jobs in cleaning services, waste collection, recycling, etc. (without mentioning the context that these are low-paid, unwanted by the majority unprestigious jobs);
- "the immigrants' criminal activity" – pieces of news on violent crimes committed by immigrants are widely disseminated and commented on; in case of no such local news, news from other countries are used (media analysts often came across such stories from Germany, for example);
- immigrants/refugees' "socio-cultural incompatibility" and the danger of changing the traditional culture and values in the country.

Here it is worth reiterating that immigrants are not a homogeneous group and the discourse presented above refers only to the part of them that dominates the news stream. In relation to this very group, terms with different meanings are used to refer to interchangeably, but always with a negative connotation - migrants, labour migrants, economic migrants, refugees, aliens, as well as other unflattering and offensive terms, which will be omitted here.

At the same time, immigrants from certain countries are presented in a very different light. When writing and speaking about them, different language and definitions are used, loaded with a positive connotation. For example, settled pensioners from the UK, the Netherlands and other EU countries (especially if they play Bulgarian folk dances in their spare time) are often cast in the image of saviours of the Bulgaria's depopulated countryside that has gripped many areas of the country.

The situation is similar with immigrants from the former USSR (mainly Russia, Moldova and Ukraine) and former Yugoslavia (North Macedonia and Serbia) who obtain Bulgarian citizenship on the basis of their "Bulgarian origin". They enjoy the media image of returning compatriots, an integral part of the Bulgarian diaspora or culturally close. Media and prominent public figures show empathy and tolerance even in cases where these immigrants speak no Bulgarian, are involved in corrupt schemes to acquire documents, have no intentions to live in Bulgaria and their goals are purely instrumental - a passport that provides more opportunities for work and travel. Culturally and socially, these immigrants, in their vast majority, are typical representatives of their countries of origin. Rarely do they resemble representatives of any social group in nowadays Bulgarian society. However, they are not presented, discussed and perceived as a threat.

The discourse of "immigrants as a threat" – with the exception of some extremely conservative and nationalist media – does not apply to the representatives of countries that have many admirers both among the members of the leading political parties and among the public at large. At the forefront are the countries of the "always with Germany, never against Russia" principle that has been strongly proclaimed over the last decades. It is extremely rare for a reader to come across a piece of news or a commentary article that presents immigrants from these two countries as a threat and associates them with the negative context described above. A similar attitude is enjoyed by most (but not all) nationals from the USA and some other European countries, including Italy and Switzerland.

Table 1 is a numerical illustration of the impact of the political and media discourses on the topic of immigrants summarized above on the attitudes of adult Bulgarians. When reading the results, the month of March 2018 is particularly noteworthy. The attitudes recorded then coincide with the period during which survey discussed below was conducted.

The vast majority of respondents accept immigrants from non-EU countries with negative feelings. Over the period 2014-2018, at least two-thirds see non-EU immigrants as the threat already mentioned. Between a quarter and a third range those who are also negatively tuned to immigrants from other EU countries. Importantly (given the representativeness of the Eurobarometer data), no less than 10% of respondents would identify themselves as Bulgarian citizens of Turkish origin and/or Muslims. This suggests that a significant proportion of them have a (strongly) positive attitude towards almost everything related to Turkey, including Turks from the Republic of Turkey settling in Bulgaria. However, their attitude is hardly as positive towards citizens of countries such as Afghanistan, Iraq, Syria or Somalia. In view of the above, it is reasonable to assume that in column five (Table 1), which reflects positive attitudes towards immigrants from non-EU countries (such as the Republic of Turkey), the

percentages are actually overrated, because it is very likely that most of the Bulgarian Turks and Muslims surveyed equated the question as asking about citizens of Turkey and did not refer to other countries (Middle East, Africa, etc.) in their answers.

Table 1. Attitude of Bulgarians towards immigrants

Date	from the EU			from outside the EU		
	Positive	Negative	I don't know	Positive	Negative	I don't know
08/11/2014	56.5%	31.8%	11.7%	23.7%	65.3%	11.0%
16/05/2015	48.4%	35.3%	16.3%	26.6%	58.6%	14.8%
07/11/2015	58.9%	29.1%	12.0%	19.4%	70.0%	10.5%
21/05/2016	60.5%	27.1%	12.3%	17.5%	72.7%	9.9%
03/11/2016	61.1%	28.0%	11.0%	14.9%	77.0%	8.1%
20/05/2017	62.7%	24.8%	12.5%	20.3%	68.0%	11.7%
05/11/2017	66.2%	25.2%	8.7%	21.4%	70.3%	8.3%
17/03/2018	61.0%	26.2%	12.8%	21.4%	66.9%	11.7%
08/11/2018	53.7%	33.7%	12.6%	15.1%	74.1%	10.8%

Source: author's calculations based on Eurobarometer data (<https://www.europarl.europa.eu/at-your-service/en/be-heard/eurobarometer/>)

In fact, about three quarters express disapproval of the immigrants from outside the EU. This is justified by the high rates of negativity registered in May and November 2016, when Hungary, Slovenia, Croatia, etc. closed their borders to prevent the use of the so-called “Balkan route for migrants”. At this moment, when the immigration issue in the media was exclusively focused on refugees/migrants from Syria, Iraq and Afghanistan, it could be seen how tolerance towards immigrants was melting away. During this period, migrants were not really defined as any other group than those constructed as a threat.

Tab.1 results as well as the dynamics of contradictory attitudes – on the one hand accepting immigrants from a given non-EU country, but not from all other third countries – reveal the existence of discriminatory attitudes towards specific groups of immigrants. This attitude is mostly determined by the countries or regions of origin and the attitudes and prejudices associated with them. The empirical results presented above are evidence that media discourse in a short time has managed to construct a very strong negative attitude towards immigrants, which (as will become apparent below) is commensurate with the attitude towards the Roma (see Fig. 1), the ethnic group with the lowest social status. Identical mechanisms have also been detected by other researchers (Tomova, 2009; Tomova, 2013; Pamporov, 2009).

The other methodological feature related to the results in Tab. 1 is the fact that many Bulgarians unconsciously (and sometimes due to lack of knowledge about exactly which countries are members of the EU) put an equal sign between Europe and the European Union. The range of countries is thus widened, and the polyvalent attitudes towards citizens of different EU member states makes it extremely difficult

to interpret the results. However, given the very large structural differences in the attitudes of Bulgaria's permanent residents towards immigrants according to their country/region of origin, it can be concluded that the majority of people are positive towards the immigrants from the EU or European residents.

Attitudes towards immigrants of the Bulgarians of reproductive age

The results of the public attitudes survey show that when respondents are asked about immigrants or circumstances related to immigrants, many of them tend to answer for the group that personifies threat. In addition, fig. 1 clearly shows that the attitude of Bulgaria's permanent residents (all ethnicities) towards immigrants (and their children) is worse than the attitude of Bulgaria's non-Roma on the same issue towards Roma.²

Figure 1. Attitudes and distances of people of reproductive age towards immigrants and the Roma in Bulgaria

Note: author's calculations

This very analysis explores the attitudes and distances towards the socially constructed image of immigrants, as perceived by the respondents with regard to their ability to critically accept or reject the information available.

² The Roma minority is the most socially excluded and living in material deprivation in the country (NSI, 2019; NSI, 2018; Tomova, 2000; Ringold, Orenstein & Wilkins, 2003; Revenga, Ringold & Tracy, 2002; Mitev, Tomova & Kostadinova, 2001).

The questionnaire has only one, but useful and workable indicator to explore distances and attitudes towards immigrants – do you approve of your child/grandchild studying in a class with several immigrant children. Before analysing the data by different features of the population, it is imperative to point out that there are grounds to argue that the indicator in question tends to overestimate to some extent the level of tolerance among Bulgarian society. Not only the immigrants, but also the attitude of respondents towards immigrant children is examined. This puts the respondents in a situation to assess a family situation as well, and not only a category of persons taken out of context and with minimal specificity.³

The following specifics of the indicator should be considered:

- the question explores attitudes towards immigrants indirectly, asking not only about them but also about their children – respondents are generally more compassionate and open to supporting immigrant families with children; the most demonised image of an immigrant in the media is that of a young single man from Asia or Africa heading for a rich EU country who has no respect for the laws and mores of European countries, and is prone to violence (especially towards women) and makes the most of the social security and healthcare systems;
- by default, questions related to children – a symbol of innocence and often perceived as victims of their parents' understandings and actions – give rise to tolerance and empathy that respondents are much less likely to declare towards adults from the same community.

Fig. 1 provides empirical grounds for two more conclusions. First, the percentages of the respondents who were unable to answer (Don't know/Can't say) are different, a statistically significant difference of proportions ($\chi^2 = 31.13$, $P < 0.001$). This result leads to the conclusion that, in general, respondents are less familiar and aware of immigrants than of Roma. There are more respondents who do not take a position on this issue when it comes to immigrants than those who declare an opinion on the same issue when it comes to Roma. If with regard to the Roma quite so many stereotypes and attitudes are already consolidated, it is likely that with regard to immigrants this process is lagging behind. There are still opportunities to change the communication narratives in the media so that immigrants are not socially constructed as just another vulnerable group. However, a more realistic prediction is that immigrants – especially those whose countries of origin are outside Europe – will end up, like the Roma, with an unattractive image among the general population.

Second, the proportion of those expressing negative attitudes about the possibility of their children or grandchildren being educated in the same class with several children of immigrants and the similar proportion of those expressing negative attitudes about the same issue regarding Roma are not statistically different ($\chi^2 = 1.57$,

³ In the Eurobarometer question on immigrants from outside the EU, each respondent can base their answer on immigrants with very different profiles at their own discretion - men, women, families with or without children, Muslims, Christians, from Africa, Asia or Europe, etc.

$P = 0.21$). This is an empirical result supporting the hypothesis that there already exists a hard core with a strong negative attitude towards the persons of different ethnicity/nationality. Identifying the causes of this negative attitude and the mechanisms by which the attitude in question is internalised by large segments of the population should become the subject of further research in near future. Some of the most significant profile characteristics of these individuals are discussed next.

Gender perspective

The results on Fig. 2 show that the differences between men and women in the percentages are negligible. In practice, they are so small that there are no statistically significant differences but one exception: the percentage of women who approve of their children attending classes together with immigrant children is 3.8 percentage points greater than the corresponding percentage for men ($\chi^2 = 4.07$, $P < 0.05$). This result refers to the claim by Heath and Richards that it is specific to OECD countries that women are more empathetic than men with respect to immigrants (Heath & Richards, 2019). The Republic of Bulgaria is not a member of the OECD yet, but aspires membership.

Figure 2. Attitudes and distances of people of reproductive age towards immigrants by gender in Bulgaria

Note: author's calculations

All other differences in the percentages on Fig. 2 are stochastic. Accordingly, the probability that one of the two sexes is less distant towards immigrants than the other is negligible. It is possible that among Bulgaria's women of reproductive age

a process of empathy or understanding towards immigrants (in particular towards their children) is taking place and is slightly ahead of an analogous process in men. In general, however, the results of the gender analysis are more in line with research arguing that the gender of respondents, even in cases where statistically significant differences between men and women are observed, is too weak a determinant and does not significantly influence the attitudes towards migrants (Rustenbach 2010; Evans & Kelley, 2019).

Age perspective

Fig. 3 reveals the attitudes towards immigrants according to respondents' age. A distribution with 7 groups is optimal and the best possible visual for presenting the data to illustrate most findings.

Figure 3. Attitudes and distances according to the age of persons of reproductive age towards immigrants in Bulgaria

Note: author's calculations

The lowest age for both sexes being 18 years and the highest (due to specifics related to fertility ages) for men being 55, while for women it is 49. It should be noted that the highest age group, that of persons aged 52 and over, consists of males only. The remaining 6 groups reveal perhaps the key finding for the age-specific analysis – among those aged 34-51, those who approve of their children/grandchildren studying in a class with immigrant children outnumber 2 or more times those who disapprove in each age subgroup. This ratio, referred to as “2 or more to 1”, can be used as a baseline level for comparisons regarding openness and tolerance. In other words,

two-thirds or more of a given age group demonstrate openness and tolerance towards immigrants. From this perspective, although the number of those who approve seemingly dominates across all age groups, it can be seen that younger individuals (22-33 year olds) are generally less open and tolerant than those in the higher age groups (34-55) and the youngest (18-21).

The ratio of those who approve of their children/grandchildren studying in a class with immigrant children to those who disapprove among those aged 22-33 is 1.5:1; the lowest ratio is observed in the 28-33 age band 1.4:1. The 22-33 age group almost perfectly overlaps with the demographic cohort of the “millennials” (“Generation Y”). According to the dominant paradigm, Generation Y are those born between 1981-1996 (Rauch, 2018), which in Fig. 3 is projected for Bulgaria with a slightly higher lower bound – those born between 1985 and 1996.

With the currently available data, one can only speculate whether Generation Y is more or less tolerant than the other two generations in the sample - Generation X (of those born before 1980-81) and Generation Z (of those born after 1997). The reason for this is an alternative explanation for the so-called key finding above. It is a perfectly plausible hypothesis that Generation Y may take a more forthright approach when declaring their attitudes on uncomfortable issues, and that other generations may more often resort to socially desirable responses.

Generation Y in Bulgaria has no first-hand awareness of the pre-1989 totalitarian system and its restrictions. This is a very significant difference between them and the Generation X, where the ratio of those who approve of their children/grandchildren studying in a class with children of immigrants to those who do not is higher – 2.2:1, i.e. they seem more open and tolerant. However, the older generations in the country know very well how the totalitarian system imposed and provided conditions for nurturing the skill of glossing over some of what is thought, of avoiding going into depth on certain topics and issues, and how, on an unconscious level, people were gradually developing en masse an ability to “hit the right answer,” i.e., to say what the government expects and wants to hear, not what they actually think. These circumstances underlie the hypothesis that the tolerance of Generation X is probably overestimated, and it may be that the differences in attitudes towards immigrants reported in the results between them and Generation Y are virtually non-existent (and even vice-versa).

However, the survey provides evidence that the Generation X are more open and tolerant. This is supported by a piece of research that describes young people in transition as having different values, focused primarily on the material values (Mitev, 2012). If this is assumed to be true, it seems logical that in their selfishness they would be less inclined to empathy and sympathy for immigrants. In any case, however, the fact that – because of the political change in 1989 – Generations X and Y have grown up and formed as individuals in very different political regimes should not be underestimated (something very specific to countries such as Bulgaria – a key prerequisite for differences with their peers in Western Europe and North America).

In Bulgaria, marketing and advertising professionals are among the few who have studied the Generation Y in more detail so far. Recently, millennials have been in their prime and more often are the new leaders, celebrities and influencers. In ad-

dition, key customers, experts and stakeholders in various economic sectors (e.g., construction, real estate, automobiles) are emerging from their midst. Generation Y are described as young persons who are committed to causes, prefer to socialise in small communities, have a balance between work and leisure, are curious about the world, have an attitude towards health and healthy eating and are disloyal/suspicious of established brands and labels. Furthermore, it has gained credibility that Bulgarian millennials differ from their peers (in fact, it is not clearly defined in what exactly) who live in Western Europe and whose childhood did not go through food crises, massive bankruptcies of banking and financial institutions, hyperinflation and large-scale impoverishment and marginalisation of many population groups such as the pensioners and the Roma (Stoyanova, 2018).

These and similar specifics that can be found in the literature can hardly be attributed as values and attitudes that generate negative attitudes towards immigrants and even more so towards the children of immigrants. It makes even more sense to argue the opposite, i.e. to imply openness and tolerance towards the different. Ross and Rouse analyse data from surveys in the United States and conclude that Generation Y's tolerance towards immigrants is 1) entirely consistent with their liberal views and 2) millennials are generally more tolerant than other generations (Ross & Rouse, 2015), i.e., the opposite of what the results of the survey under discussion reveal. This appears as an additional argument in favour of the hypothesis outlined above that it is possible to overestimate the tolerance of Generation X due to the specificity of the measurement method and the indicator itself which might distort to some extent the attitude towards immigrants.

Another study on the Generation Y's attitudes toward immigrants is by a research team from the University of Chicago. Generation Y is described as very tolerant with the specification that within the generation itself there are some heterogeneous and contradictory attitudes towards immigrants determined by ethnic, racial and political characteristics. For instance, 64% of millennials who voted Donald Trump in the 2016 presidential election support deporting all undocumented immigrants; 86% of white millennials say they feel they are full and equal citizens of the United States, while among African Americans only 56% feel this way (Cohen et al., 2018). In fact, these opinions demonstrate that the less homogeneous a generation is, the more complex it is to explain attitudes across "typical" generational characteristics. Heterogeneity is a consequence of social processes and policies that have generated social exclusion, discrimination, educational and income inequalities, as well as imbalances of social and human capital among different subgroups in society. It is also possible that the differences analysed among the Bulgarian generations are a product of a similar heterogeneity.

The survey data do not provide sufficient observations for an analysis of the structural weight of attributes such as ethnicity (insufficient observations by age group except among ethnic Bulgarians), religion and political preferences (not included in the questionnaire). Research focusing on individual generations (with particular emphasis on X and Y) is also needed to clarify the mechanisms that led to the atypical differences in tolerance levels detected among members of Generation Y and whether and to what extent the differences identified via the survey actually exist.

The determinants of why such a significant proportion of young people in the country openly declares intolerant attitudes towards the different and the vulnerable groups and communities should also be identified.

Family perspective

This very indicator contains an essential element - the presence or absence of own child/children. An important research question is whether the presence/absence of respondents' own children influences their attitudes towards immigrants. Does having children/grandchildren of one's own – a de facto self-interest – reinforce discriminatory and intolerant attitudes towards immigrants? If immigrants are perceived as a threat, their children should probably be also part of that threat. Thus, parents and grandparents would logically, as an express of concern, wish to keep their children away from such a threat.

Fig. 4 shows that respondents who have no children of their own are more likely to see a situation of Bulgarian and immigrant children studying together as a danger than those who are de facto parents. It seems that children, in parallel with the commitments and activities that parents perform alongside them, not only develop parental capacity, but also help to develop tolerance and non-discriminatory attitudes towards those who are different (if not in reality, then at least on a declarative level).

Figure 4. Attitudes and distances of people of reproductive age towards immigrants in Bulgaria according to age and whether they have children

Note: author's calculations

Thus, it makes sense that when assessments of parental capacity are being made, the assessors should also start taking into account the level of tolerance, and the non-discriminatory attitudes and behaviour towards the vulnerable and the different that parents/carers demonstrate. Those who have the potential to pass on tolerance and non-discrimination to their children, alongside all other aspects (housing, education, physical and mental health, economic opportunities, etc.), should be valued and promoted.

In addition, high levels of tolerance and non-discriminatory behaviour should be incentivised through the policies and measures, including financially. For example, parents who encourage their children to study in mixed classes/grades where at least 20% of the pupils are children of immigrants or from vulnerable groups should be entitled to benefits such as vouchers for clothes and school supplies (pens, notebooks, textbooks, etc., including, if necessary, tablets and laptops) and free access to training and courses (on paid online platforms) with the leading teachers in key subjects such as Bulgarian, mathematics, foreign languages and others, which are linked to their personal preferences for applying to high schools and universities. This same category of students can also be provided with free access to summer schools and training camps during the holidays.

The lack of children in the 40+ age group (Generation X) overturns the ratio of those who approve to those who disapprove that their child attends a class with immigrant children. The share of parents who approve sharply goes down. The tolerant are now less than half of all respondents in the age and no children group. This emerges as a specific subgroup within the generation that seems much more hostile to immigrants and alienated from the mainstream values of the majority of their peers.

Figure 5. Attitudes and distances according to marital status of persons of reproductive age towards immigrants in Bulgaria

Note: author's calculations

Among the 40+ age group, the lack of children seems to go hand in hand with lower levels of tolerance (Fig. 4). It can be hypothesised that the lack of a spouse (or partner(s) now and in the recent past) also has a negative impact on respondents aged 40+. This is the only age group (40-45) in which those who disapprove the children of Bulgarian nationals and immigrants studying together outnumber those who approve.

It is also noteworthy that in the age group 34-39 the ratio is 3 to 1 in favour of those who are tolerant and non-discriminating, which does not suggest such a sudden reversal of structure. Although the number of observations in these cuts are smaller than statistically recommended, the findings in sociological terms are important and appear to be substantively valid.

In fact, as age increases, intolerance towards those who are different begins to increase, but especially among those population groups who, for whatever reasons, have been experiencing certain deficits, in this case the lack of child/children and/or partner(s). Generally speaking, this pattern is a kind of objectification of a condition that the more isolated and uninvolved people are with a particular situation, the more likely they do not know it well enough; they are more susceptible to suggestions that may sound logical in some respects but are definitely false or misleading.

The survey provided data to analyse two features related to the respondents' family situation. There is plenty of reasons to believe that the family situation influences the level of tolerance. The foundations of one's attitude to the world and upbringing are laid during the first seven years precisely in the family. Parents are the first from whom children learn patterns of behaviour and values, many of which they later replicate (albeit in their own unique style).

To date, there have not been reported many proponents of gender-neutral early childhood education in Bulgaria. It can be argued that it is not typical for the nowadays Bulgarian family. The practice is to raise children according to their biological sex. For example, the vast majority of parents will not accept a doll as a gift for their child if he is a boy. Furthermore, traditions in upbringing encourage the distribution of family duties and responsibilities according to stereotypes of 'male and female work'. In short, raising children in a Bulgarian family is not gender-neutral (of course, there are exceptions).

Above, it was found that the gender of the respondents had no significant impact in terms of tolerance towards immigrants. This suggests that considering the attitudes towards immigrants, children are brought up the same way regardless of their gender and also that it is likely that certain key specifics related to family play a role with regard to tolerance towards immigrants.

The survey results confirm this in at least two areas - 1) marital status - whether a person lives alone or is married, etc. and 2) whether a person has children of their own. In the first case, there was a statistically significant relationship between marital status and the respondents' level of tolerance ($\chi^2= 13.34$, $P<0.05$), with Cramer's $V=0.079$ (with adjustment for non-stochastic error – bias) and $V=0.066$ (unadjusted) indicating that the relationship of this determinant is commensurate in strength with education (as will be seen below). The results as already mentioned show that singles and unmarried become the least tolerant as age progresses.

In the second case, a statistically significant relationship between having children of one's own and the level of tolerance towards immigrants is established ($\chi^2=6.72, P<0.05$). Cramer's values practically duplicate those in the first case and differ only after the third decimal point. Those who have their own children are more empathetic and tolerant toward immigrants than those who do not.

Educational attainment perspective

Quality education that lacks manipulation and propaganda of stereotypes and prejudice, that encourages critical thinking and rejects the easy acceptance of unproven or controversial claims, seems like a workable solution to overcoming intolerance and discrimination. It is difficult to ascertain, however, whether Bulgaria currently has an educational system that can provide exactly this kind of social reproduction of the population.

A longer stay in the education system implies more opportunities for teachers to change (if they are racist, negative or anti-human) or reinforce (if they are humanistic, positive and open to diversity) existing attitudes towards the different, the vulnerable and, in particular, towards immigrants. The educational system is called to counteract in cases of negative influences from family, friends, informal groups and the media (including social media) that openly promote hatred, violence and intolerance. Eventually, the point of any education system is to provide knowledge, skills and values, that due to limited parental capacity many families are unable to provide to their children.

Figure 6. Attitudes and distances according to educational attainment of the persons of reproductive age towards immigrants in Bulgaria

Note: author's calculations

The results in Fig. 6 illustrate tolerance and non-discrimination towards immigrants (and their children) in terms of respondents' education. The observed minimal differences in the relative shares (within 4 percentage points) between those with tertiary education and those with secondary education are random, i.e. the differences in percentages are not statistically significant. In practice, this generally means that four or more years in the higher education system does not imply increased tolerance, even at the declarative level (the vast majority of the respondents in the sample graduated in Bulgaria).

In the totalitarian communistic past, many excellent specialists could not (dared not) apply their analytical skills outside their narrow specialisation and assess impartially events such as the Revival process⁴ [Vazroditelen protses] or the real state of the economy of the People's Republic of Bulgaria. It is also possible that currently, when it comes to critical thinking skills and scientifically correct knowledge in the social sciences and humanities, the higher education system functions in a similar manner and students do not receive the knowledge and analytical skills they need to critically think of and assess social problems, situations and challenges.

It is also noteworthy that those who have completed primary education (or lower) are more open and tolerant towards immigrants than those who are far more educated. More than two thirds of the less educated declare empathy towards immigrants and their children; less than 18% express a negative attitude towards them. The poorly educated spend fewer years in school, respectively learn more through experience and communication than in the education system. They spend much less time under a targeted pedagogical influence that has the methodological arsenal to build different worldviews, including a limited one that interferes with critical and analytical evaluation on certain topics of everyday political and social life.

Sound research has argued for a strong causal link between educational attainment and anti-immigrant attitudes in Western Europe and North America. For example, there is statistical evidence and estimates that in Western Europe, each additional year in high school reduces opposition to immigration and the belief that immigrants erode the quality of life in a country by 10 percentage points, and that more time spent in school leads to more tolerance towards immigrants (Cavaille & Marshal, 2017). Heath and Richards find that in OECD countries, education and age are the determinants that draw lines of division in the attitudes towards immigrants from poor non-European countries, with the role of higher education carrying more weight even than income and gender (Heath & Richards, 2019).

In Germany, each year of schooling reduces the likelihood of an individual being overly concerned about immigration by approximately 6 percentage points. Maternal education has also been found to significantly influence children's attitudes towards immigrants (Margaryan et. al., 2018). Hainmueller and Hiscox's analysis provides

⁴ The Revival Process refers to a policy of forced assimilation practiced by Bulgaria's communist government in the 1980s. The policy involved the ethnic cleansing of Bulgaria's ethnic Turkish minority, which eventually culminated in the forced expulsion of about 360 thousand ethnic Turks in 1989.

quantitative arguments that the more educated tertiary graduates are much less likely to be racist and value cultural diversity more than others. They are also more likely to understand and accept that immigration generally generates benefits for the host country's economy (Hainmueller & Hiscox, 2007).

Borgonovi and Pokropek argue that more educated people are less likely to oppose immigration than less educated people, finding that 60% of the difference in attitudes towards immigration is due to how people conceptualise the feeling of threat (Borgonovi & Pokropek, 2019). In fact, this is exactly what was meant above when referring to the portrayal of immigrants as a threat by the media and particular politicians and the opportunities for critical and analytical conceptualization of false, distorted, or incorrect information by large segments of the population.

In the context of these and other similar research, the statistical analysis of the results under discussion testifies to the existence of a relationship between the level of education and the respondents' attitudes towards immigrants and their children in Bulgaria (statistically significant, $\chi^2= 16.04$, $P<0.01$). Apart from the nature of this relationship, already commented in detail above, the question of the strength of this relationship deserves attention. Cramer's coefficient $V=0.06$ (with adjustment for non-stochastic error – bias) and $V=0.07$ (unadjusted) is an indicator of a relationship that can be defined as moderate to weak, based on traditional interpretation of the Cramer's coefficient (Akoglu, 2018; Cohen, 1988; Kim, 2017).

Recently, however, possibly due to the need for greater precision in medical research estimates, alternative interpretative models have been proposed, with V values in the range 0.00-0.10 being defined as negligible, and between 0.10-0.20 as an indicator of a weak association (Lee, 2016). Regardless of which of the two approaches is taken, the general conclusion is that the educational system in the country has not been and continues to be underutilised to support the processes of social inclusion, the development of skills and attitudes of tolerance, sensitivity to discriminatory practices and empathy.

Type of locality perspective

Fig. 7 aims to illustrate the relationship between the type of locality in which respondents live and their levels of tolerance towards immigrants. Statistical analysis shows that such a relationship exists in Bulgaria (statistically significant, $\chi^2= 26.91$, $P<0.001$). In short, the level of tolerance of people differs from one place to another.

Regarding the strength of this correlation, Cramer's coefficient $V=0.079$ (with correction for non-stochastic error – bias) and $V=0.09$ (uncorrected) is an indicator that – like the relationship between education and tolerance – it can be defined as moderate to weak. It is also possible to define the relationship as negligibly weak in case a more stringent criterion is set (Rea & Parker, 1992). In fact, when designing measures related to the integration of immigrants, the type of locality should be taken into account, i.e. policies should be tailored to it, without expecting it to play more than the role of a significant and important context.

Figure 7. Attitudes and distances towards immigrants in Bulgaria according to the type of locality in which the persons live (aged 18-55)

Note: author's calculations

What this statistical analysis does not have the potential to reveal is whether people choose the type of locality they live in not only according to the dictates of their financial capabilities (which is certain, given that buying a home is a financial transaction), but also according to their level of tolerance. Findings of observers of the real estate market in the country show that when selecting a flat/house, buyers often set conditions that stimulate segregation, such as the property being located away from immigrant accommodation/detention centres, from settlements with a predominantly Roma population, or that no 'minorities' should live in the immediate neighbourhood – an example of discriminatory attitudes that partly determine the address of residence. A national survey conducted in 2017 showed that a large majority of the Bulgarian nationals believe that refugees/immigrants should live in closed type detention centres (Mantarova, 2018).

The gathering of a majority of intolerant and discriminatory people in certain localities shapes the values and attitudes towards the different of their children who grow up and socialise in such communities. In these communities, for example, racist qualifiers, ethnic slurs and intolerant behaviour are sanctioned neither by parents nor the community. This illustrates how a particular locality can influence generational levels of tolerance. The most unfortunate combination of the materialisation of a lack of tolerance and openness is a vicious circle in which the level of tolerance shrinks and alienation and resentment towards those who are different (including immigrants) grows generation after generation. While there is no quantitative evidence of this, there is reason to hypothesise that a similar process has occurred in small towns across the country (see Fig. 7, Small Town column).

Regarding immigration issues, it should be noted that the processes in Bulgaria are at an early stage. There are still no distinct immigrant neighbourhoods, as there are in most European capitals. The exceptions are small parts in particular areas in the capital – apartment blocks in the residential areas of “Tolstoy” and “Svoboda” in the vicinity of the shopping centre “Iliantsi” and in the area around the Women’s Market (Zhenski pazar) in Sofia. In practice, interaction between the local population and particular larger immigrant groups (not at individual level) can be seen in these places and in the vicinity of the three centres for illegal immigrants in Sofia – “Voenna rampa”, “Vrazhdebna” and “Ovcha Kupel”. In fact, hundreds of thousands of people in the capital see or learn facts about immigration mainly or only from the media, friends and acquaintances. Neither communicating nor working together with immigrants is a part of their daily lives. Compared to the capital, in other types of localities both the number and the relative share of immigrants (especially those seen as a threat) is significantly lower.

The survey results show that the greatest uncertainty concerning immigrants is detected among the population that lives in villages: nearly 16% could not answer the question. They were unable to tell whether their children/grandchildren should study together with children of immigrants. This opens room for a potential growth in terms of tolerance. With the well-designed approach and communication, Bulgaria’s villages can become welcoming centres for immigrants and this can help solve the severe challenges: rejuvenation and ceasing of depopulation. This percentage is also an indicator that, regardless of prejudices and attitudes, the severe demographic situation, especially the lack of young people in the villages, is leading to the erosion of some traditional attitudes of their inhabitants such as mistrust and fear of foreigners.

At the opposite site, in terms of uncertainty, are the residents of the capital – Sofia (only 5% are undecided in their opinion about immigrants), and large cities with a population of over 100 thousand people (10%). Although the percentage values in this case are few times lower, their corresponding absolute values are much higher – reaching a population of 50 thousand or more people living in a relatively compact areas in the cities of Sofia, Plovdiv, etc. Given that this is a population of reproductive and working age, bringing these people into the group of the tolerant and compassionate should be a priority target of any inclusion policy.

In smaller cities, the shares of those unable to answer are around 14%, and usually as the proportion of those who do not know or cannot answer increases, the proportion of those who strongly disapprove and are intolerant decreases. The exception are the small towns, where the increased proportion of those cannot say and do not know is due to a shrinking of the group of tolerant. These observations imply that the media (electronic, print and social) succeed most in negatively stigmatising immigrants in small towns. This is also where the greatest challenges for immigrant integration policies are, because the process of social inclusion occurs in the context of the most unfavourable possible conditions in terms of social distances, attitudes and tough job market.

At first glance it may seem a bit illogical, but the city with the most immigrants – the capital – demonstrates the highest level of tolerance. However, it is also the most economically developed place in the country. It is followed by the other regional

cities, which are respectively the regional economic leaders. At the tail end of tolerance are small towns, which structurally lag behind villages in terms of tolerance. This probably has something to do with the changes that have taken place in some of Bulgaria's villages (especially in those close to the big cities) in recent years: a trend for more and more people with high incomes and education to settle there.

International perspective

Fig. 8 shows a different perspective towards immigrants. They should not be seen as a major source of problems and trouble. A positive correlation between GDP per capita (calculated at purchasing power parity) and the relative share of immigrants is observed ($r=0.65$, $p<0.0001$). This correlation does not mean that more immigrants in Bulgaria would automatically generate higher economic growth, but it definitely shows that the one-sided view of “immigrants as a threat” in economic terms is the wrong approach.

Figure 8. Immigration and gross domestic product in Europe, 2017

Source: data from United Nations, Department of Economic and Social Affairs and World Bank, International Comparison Program database

The alternative point of view can be called “immigrants as opportunity”. They are important for particular sectors of the economy, the labour market and business because they offer opportunities for the local populations to learn new things, bring diversity, provide new approaches to existing problems and a different perspective. As the European experience shows, immigrants generally have potential to support

economic growth and development. If immigration processes are properly managed, immigrants can contribute economically (Fig. 8). Indeed, this seems the right approach for measures and policies towards immigrants: to see them as an opportunity rather than a burden that society should try to get rid of, which is economically disadvantageous.

In 2017, the relative share of immigrants in the Republic of Bulgaria was 2.2% of the total population. In the same year, it was 19% in Austria, 14.8% in Germany, 10% in Italy, 12.1% in the Netherlands and 29.6% in Switzerland (United Nations, Department of Economic and Social Affairs. Population Division, 2017). For 2017, the Republic of Bulgaria reported a per capita GDP at purchasing power parity (PPP) of \$20.9 thousand. The same indicator for Austria was \$53.9 thousand, for Germany – \$52 thousand, for Italy – \$41.2 thousand, for the Netherlands – \$54.5 thousand, and in Switzerland it reached \$66.4 thousand. In fact, this is an illustration of the fact that immigration is not an obstacle or a threat to economic growth and development. Of course, immigrants alone are not and cannot be the engine of economic growth.

Activity perspective

It is important to know whether those who work are more tolerant than those who (for one reason or another) do not exercise their right to work. The proportion of the tolerant among those who work and those who do not work is roughly the same (Fig. 9). Structurally, however, there are significant differences between the working and non-working populations in terms of the shares of those

Figure 9. Attitudes and distances towards immigrants in Bulgaria according to the activity status of persons aged 18-55

Note: author’s calculations

who do not want their children to be in class with immigrant children or are unable to answer. Overall, the non-working population seems a bit more empathic, non-discriminatory and tolerant towards immigrants.

The statistical analysis shows that the relationship between labour market participation and tolerance towards immigrants is statistically significant ($\chi^2= 25.99$, $P<0.001$). The type of activities according to which the respondents were categorized (1. working, 2. studying and 3. neither working nor studying) and their level of tolerance were correlated. An indicator of the strength of this relationship is Cramer's coefficient $V=0.086$ (with correction for non-stochastic error - bias) and $V=0.093$ (uncorrected). The correlation can be defined as moderate to weak, but of all the relationships discussed so far, this one is the strongest and impactful.

However, the group of students is very different. The results identify it as one of the most problematic given that the relative proportion of tolerant respondents is less than half of the respondents in the group itself. Again, the question of how the education system influences the building of a cohesive and integrated society, open to all its members, arises. Further, it becomes clear again that the potential of the system is not sufficiently used for integration purposes and the inclusive education remains an unrealised project and challenge for the time being.

It is important to point out that the students in Fig. 9 are adults and study because of their choice, without the institutional coercion of the state. This is a group to which special measures should be addressed through the institutions which they attend, i.e. measures should be targeted at universities, colleges, academies and postgraduate organisations.

Income perspective

The major questions related to household income and members' attitudes towards immigrants are 1) whether there is a relationship between the income level of the respondents and their attitude towards immigrants and if so 2) which households are more likely to show more tolerance and empathy – the more affluent or those households that are more or less financially squeezed.

About 71% of the respondents agreed to indicate the net income of their households. The high percentage of refusals requires the clarification that the conclusions that follow are to some extent tentative, especially when the structural relationships under discussion are not clear and explicit. It is also important to note that the respondents who reported the highest incomes in the survey are not the group of the richest people in the country, who are hard to cover via the survey method.

The data disaggregated on Fig. 10 (3 income groups) allow for statistical analysis of the presence of a relationship between the respondents' household income and their levels of tolerance towards immigrants. The data disaggregated on Fig. 11 do not allow such an analysis because the observations in the different groups are small in number or missing (for example, no respondent declared a household income between BGN 2500-2999) to apply a non-parametric method. However, Fig. 11 has its merits in terms of some important details that are blurred when data are merged into

Figure 10. Attitudes and distances towards immigrants in Bulgaria according to household income, respondents aged 18-55 (3 income groups)

Note: author's calculations

Figure 11. Attitudes and distances towards immigrants in Bulgaria by household income, respondents aged 18-55

Note: author's calculations

larger groups and refusals are discarded: for example, the high tolerance among the lowest income households as well as the distribution of attitudes of those respondents who refused to declare the net income of the households in which they live (see row Refusal to answer).

The statistical analysis shows a statistically significant relationship: households differ in their level of tolerance towards immigrants according to their income ($\chi^2= 14.82$, $P<0.05$). Cramer's $V=0.071$ (with correction for non-stochastic error – bias) and $V=0.08$ (uncorrected) indicates that it can be defined as moderate to weak. However, if one is to compare it with the other determinants examined above, it is commensurate in strength with the type of locality and has a stronger impact than education.

Structurally, the results unequivocally show that the persons from the highest income households (over 3 thousand Bulgarian levs) are the most intolerant towards immigrants and their children. It should be borne in mind however, that the percentages are based on a very small number of respondents who live in households with such incomes ($N=48$), which certainly distorts the representativeness of the result. The situation is similar concerning the impressively high tolerance among the poorest earners whose reported household income was below BGN 500 ($N=86$). In addition, among the poorest there might be a higher proportion of respondents who were trying to 'guess' a 'correct' and socially desirable response. Given this, it is not possible to categorically conclude that the financial elites are highly intolerant and that the poorest and most financially excluded are among the most empathic people. Nevertheless, these results deserve further research and analysis.

Given the above, survey results show that respondents from households with incomes between BGN 2000-2499 are among the most tolerant, and here, if there is a distortion of the percentages, it is due to the possibility that many respondents might have refused to indicate their real income and ended up in the missing data group, but not for statistical reasons because the number of respondents is satisfactory ($N=317$). If this very income group is used as a point of reference for comparison, it can be concluded that as income decreases, the level of tolerance remains stable, and respectively the proportion of those who do not know and cannot say increases.

If these "relatively wealthy" 48 people are excluded and data are disaggregated into 2 groups – 1) households with incomes below BGN 1000 and 2) those with incomes between BGN 1000-2500, the statistical analysis now shows that there is no significant relationship between respondents' household income and their level of tolerance ($\chi^2= 3.33$, $P>0.05$). The same occurs in the situation where only the groups with persons from households with incomes between BGN 500-2499 are analysed ($\chi^2= 4.03$, $P>0.05$), i.e. again no relationship between income levels and tolerance levels.

From a research point of view, this is perhaps the most plausible conclusion in this case, given all the statistical and methodological problems arising from the high proportion of refusals when respondents were asked about their income. A major challenge remains to study this issue in detail, because it is difficult to imagine the role of income as negligible or insignificant in the consumerist society which we live in.

Conclusions

From what has been presented so far, it is evident that there is no strong and distinct determinant that on its own stands out above the others. In fact, the level of tolerance of the country's population aged 18-55 is influenced by multiple determinants of similar strength.

With the exception of income, where the results are very interesting, but based on data of low reliability, it can be concluded that an important role in terms of attitudes and distances towards immigrants is played by age, the working situation (activity) of the people, the family situation, the locality in which they live (the dominant social norms and specifics of culture) and their educational attainment.

In general, young people (22-33) are less tolerant than those in the middle age groups (34-55) and the youngest (18-21). Respondents who have no children of their own are more likely to see danger in children of immigrants and local population studying together than the respondents who actually have kids. In the group of those aged 40 and over, who have no children of their own and/or who have not previously been married or cohabiting (living together with a partner), intolerance and hostility reach the highest and most worrying dimensions.

Furthermore, troublesome is that four or more years spent in the tertiary education do not significantly increase tolerance.

The level of tolerance of the people also varies in different types of localities. Immigrants are the most stigmatised and face the strongest negative attitudes towards them in small urban settlements. In the capital, which is a specific settlement with the highest number of immigrants but also with the best opportunities for entrepreneurship and professional opportunities, the highest level of tolerance towards immigrants was detected.

Viewed from an international perspective, the situation suggests that the right approach to measures and policies towards immigrants involves seeing them as an opportunity, not as a threat, an obstacle and a burden that society should try to get rid of. Rejecting immigrants demographically, economically and socially seems an expensive, unsustainable and unprofitable solution.

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